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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

This data review provides an overview of the global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), a tool developed by Sabina Alkire and Maria Emma Santos and launched in the 2010 Human Development Report to measure acute poverty through non-monetary deprivations in health, education, and living standards. The MPI, calculated using the Alkire-Foster method, captures both the incidence and intensity of poverty and is widely used for policy and monitoring purposes. It is based on ten weighted indicators aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). While the index's broad coverage and conceptual clarity are strengths, it faces critiques regarding its dual cutoff method, equal weighting of dimensions, and the exclusion of some indicators. This review also highlights the availability of MPI data for countries relevant to Discuss Data, and discusses current limitations in indicator coverage. The MPI remains a valuable instrument for comparative poverty analysis despite its conceptual and methodological challenges.

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Data Review – Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI)

The global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) is a universal tool used to assess acute poverty by examining several aspects of deprivation in the areas of “health, education, and living standards” (12). It was introduced for the 2010 Human Development Report and created by Sabina Alkire and Maria Emma Santos, drawing on a framework developed by the Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHI) in collaboration with the Human Development Report Office of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) (12; Dotter/Klasen 2017: 2). The global MPI is published annually (12).

Unlike sole monetary poverty measures, such as the US\$1.90/day (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4) income thresholds, the global MPI also considers overlapping non-monetary deprivations people face simultaneously (12; 6). This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of poverty, particularly in developing countries, as well as for comparisons across time, regions, and demographic groups (7). The global MPI covers over 100 countries and more than 6 billion people, with detailed disaggregation “by age group, rural/urban area, subnational regions, and gender of the household head” (6).

Methodological Foundation

The MPI is calculated using the Alkire-Foster (AF) method, an approach based on counting deprivations to capture the complexity of multidimensional poverty (7). It identifies individuals as poor if their weighted deprivation score meets or exceeds a defined threshold (7). According to this method, “a person [...] is considered multidimensionally poor if they are deprived in a third or more of the weighted indicators” (12, video 00:53-01:00). These indicators, along with their corresponding Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Weight of Dimensions and Corresponding Indicators

Dimension	Indicator	Weight	SDG
Health (1/3)	Nutrition	1/6	SDG 2: Zero Hunger
	Child mortality	1/6	SDG 3: Health and Well-being
Education (1/3)	Years of schooling	1/6	SDG 4: Quality Education
	School attendance	1/6	SDG 4: Quality Education
Living Standards (1/3)	Cooking fuel	1/18	SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
	Sanitation	1/18	SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation
	Drinking water	1/18	SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation
	Electricity	1/18	SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
	Housing	1/18	SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
	Assets	1/18	SDG 1: No Poverty

(source: presentation after 12)

The MPI is computed as the product of the two components:

- Incidence (H): “the proportion (expressed as a percentage) of the population who are multidimensionally poor“ (7)
- Intensity (A): “the average percentage of weighted indicators in which poor people are deprived” (7)

The MPI value is then calculated as $MPI = H * A$ producing a score between 0 (no poverty) and 1 (“universal poverty”) (7).

The global MPI relies on “high-quality household survey datasets” (11), e.g., from the Demographic Health Surveys (DHS) and UNICEF’s Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS) (11).

The methodology of the global MPI has evolved to improve conceptual robustness, data comparability, and policy relevance. A key revision took place in 2018 when five indicators – “nutrition, child mortality, years of schooling, housing and assets” (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 3) – were redefined. For instance, the nutrition indicator was updated to incorporate individual-level information on any household member, rather than only women and children, thus addressing previous bias in measurement (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 6-7).

According to Alkire and Jahan (2018: 4) the indicators used in the updated national MPI are selected based on a set of guiding principles designed to ensure broad data coverage, conceptual clarity, and international comparability. To be included, indicators for the global MPI must be available for a minimum of 75 countries and cover at least 3.5 billion people (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4). Furthermore, it “must be compelling, [...] intuitive and easy to understand” (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4). International comparability is enhanced by “minimizing the inclusion of indicators with different meanings across countries” (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4) and by clearly communicating any inconsistencies that remain (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4). Where possible, the data should allow for disaggregation by age and region, and the comparability of results must be reliable across different weighting schemes and poverty thresholds (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 4). Despite these guidelines, certain compromises are sometimes necessary: For instance, indicators related to land ownership and livestock were excluded due to both data constraints and conceptual issues, even though their inclusion might have strengthened the index (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 5). In such cases, trial measures were implemented to empirically assess the impact of various indicator choices before finalising the revisions (Alkire/Jahan 2018: 5).

Critiques

The MPI’s “breadth of country-coverage and its international comparability” (Dotter/Klasen 2017: 5) are among the key advantages highlighted in the literature. Nonetheless, the MPI is not without conceptual and empirical shortcomings.

Several criticisms have been raised regarding its construction and application. Dotter and Klasen (2017: 3), while recognising some strengths, point to issues with the dual cutoff approach used in the MPI. This method involves two stages: “first a cut-off within each dimension or indicator is applied”; “then poverty across dimensions is aggregated, and the second cut-off is applied to identify poverty across dimensions” (Dotter/Klasen 2017: 3). This system can create confusion, as it may classify people as deprived in multiple dimensions without labelling them as poor overall (Dotter/Klasen 2017: 9). Additionally, “it violates monotonicity of poverty measurement” (Dotter/Klasen 2017: 9-10), since individuals below the second threshold are treated as non-poor regardless of the number of deprivations they face (Dotter/Klasen 2017: 9-10).

Another concern is the equal weighting of the three dimensions – 1/3 each for health, education, and living standards – which means that someone can be classified as multidimensionally poor if their household is deprived in just over a third of the weighted indicators (Bernards 2023: 1380, 1382). Furthermore, the MPI does not explicitly address employment-related aspects, such as the nature, duration, and intensity, or the conditions under which people work and commute – factors that are crucial to understanding poverty in many contexts (Bernards 2023: 1390).

From a more fundamental perspective, some scholars criticise the MPI for being descriptive but not relational. Bernards (2023) argues that while the MPI identifies deprivation “bundles”, it fails to account for the structural or political roots of poverty, thereby potentially depoliticising and decontextualising poverty analysis (Bernards 2023: 1377, 1384).

In sum, the MPI is an important step forward in measuring global poverty. Though, it is important to keep questioning its underlying assumptions, indicator selection, and political implications it might carry.

Using the MPI

MPI data is freely accessible through the OPHI’s online platform and interactive databank with no login required. The MPI is explained in detail on their [website](#), and offers, next to detailed texts and explanations also an explanatory video with subtitles (12). The global MPI is a valuable analytical tool for researchers, policymakers, and international organisations. It helps identify:

- “Who is poor and how they are poor” (12)
- Poverty patterns across “ethnic group, urban/rural area, subnational region, and age groups, as well as other key household and community characteristics” (12)
- Trends in poverty reduction or intensification over time (7)

The global MPI also offers data for countries relevant to Discuss Data such as Armenia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, and Uzbekistan (see table 2). Of the 15 for Discuss Data relevant countries, the MPI covers nine. Values for these nine countries (Armenia, Georgia,

Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan) stem from the DHS and the MICS household surveys. Indicators such as nutrition or child mortality are sometimes missing (e.g., Ukraine and Uzbekistan), potentially affecting cross-country comparability (5). Furthermore, for only two of the 15 countries – Armenia and Uzbekistan – there is also national MPI data available (see table 2).

Table 2: Discuss Data Relevant Country Coverage – Global and National MPI

Country	Global Comparisons (4 total)	Year	Survey	National MPI Publications
Armenia	Aggregate Measures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty 	2015 - 2016	DHS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launched in 2016 by the National Statistical Service of the Republic of Armenia • National MPI made of 5 dimensions: basic needs, housing, education, labour, health
	Headcount Ratio of Poverty <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day 			
	Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) 			
	Contribution of Indicators (National) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 			
Azerbaijan	No data			No results
Belarus	No data			No results
Estonia	No data			No results
Georgia	Aggregate Measures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty 	2018	MICS	No results
	Headcount Ratio of Poverty <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day 			
	Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) 			

	<p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 			
Kazakhstan	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty <p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day <p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) <p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 	2015	MICS	No results
Kyrgyzstan	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty <p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day <p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) <p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 	2018	MICS	No results
Latvia	No data			No results
Lithuania	No data			No results
Moldova	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) 	2012	MICS	No results

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) Vulnerability to poverty 			
	<p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPI headcount Severe Poverty \$2.15/day 			
	<p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) 			
	<p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage contribution Absolute contribution 			
Russia	No data			No results
Tajikistan	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) Intensity of Poverty (A) Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) Vulnerability to poverty 	2017	DHS	No results
	<p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPI headcount Severe Poverty \$2.15/day 			
	<p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) 			
	<p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage contribution Absolute contribution 			
Turkmenistan	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) Intensity of Poverty (A) Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) Vulnerability to poverty 	2019	MICS	No results
	<p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MPI headcount Severe Poverty \$2.15/day 			

	<p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (1) - (10) 			
	<p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 			
Ukraine	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty 	2012	MICS	No results
	<p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day 			
	<p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (2) - (10) • Areas not available: (1) Nutrition 			
	<p>Contribution of Indicators (National)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 			
Uzbekistan	<p>Aggregate Measures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headcount ratio of Multi-dimensional Poverty (H) • Intensity of Poverty (A) • Multi-dimensional Poverty Index (MPI) • Vulnerability to poverty 	2021 - 2022	MICS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report is “a collaborative effort between UNDP, OPHI, and the Center for Economic Research and Reforms under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan” (3) • Pilot Multi-dimensional Poverty Index Report of 2023
	<p>Headcount Ratio of Poverty</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPI headcount • Severe Poverty • \$2.15/day 			
	<p>Deprivation in Indicators (National; Censored headcount ratio)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Areas available (out of 10): (2) - (10) • Areas not available: (1) Nutrition 			

	Contribution of Indicators (National) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage contribution • Absolute contribution 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considers “multiple dimensions of poverty, including Basic Infrastructure and Living Standards, Health and Social Capital, Financial Inclusion and Employment.” (3)
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(sources: 3; 5; 8)

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Note

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